

THE STUDENT VOICE FRAMEWORK:

INTRODUCTION FOR STAFF RESPONSIBLE FOR DEPARTMENTAL STUDENT VOICE ACTIVITY

Welcome to this research-informed¹ peer reviewed² Student Voice Framework. The Framework provides staff responsible for departmental student voice activity with a suggested step by step approach to ensuring that your system is consistent, transparent, and effective. The Framework aims to ensure that:

- Every student who wishes to provide feedback has the opportunity to do so quickly, easily and ‘on the university’s time’.
- Every student providing feedback receives an individual response to their contribution.
- Student Voice meetings are a forum for the celebration of good practice and active co-creation of solutions to perceived issues – not a forum for gathering complaints.
- Student representatives are empowered to be change makers - not messengers.
- Actions identified within Student Voice meetings do not fall away: they are noted, tracked and completed in a timely and transparent manner.
- All students (regardless of whether they chose to provide feedback) are aware of actions resulting from student feedback.

[This Introduction](#) is Document A.

Document B, ‘[Student Voice Timeline: Staff Planner](#)’ will enable you to plan each step of the Student Voice journey across the academic year.

Document C, ‘[Student Voice: The Staff Guide](#)’, is a practical guide for sharing with all departmental staff.

The associated toolkit of twelve template documents/guides is designed to ensure consistency and transparency in the collection, collation, and actioning of - and closure of the loop on - feedback provided by students. The accompanying pack contains the following documents:

1. [Student voice timeline template - for students](#)
2. [Student Rep briefing template](#)
3. [Student Voice: The Student Guide](#)
4. [SVM survey: guide to setting up – for staff](#)
5. [SVM feedback request slide](#)
6. [Comments & responses document template](#)
7. [SVM 1 agenda template](#)
8. [Rolling action plan template](#)
9. [‘What have we done with your feedback’ slide template](#)
10. [SVM 2 agenda template](#)
11. [SVM 3 agenda template](#)
12. [Ongoing Action Points Carried Forward template](#)

Please feel free to amend for your own setting, but please credit the Framework and documentation to Andrea Todd. In the spirit of tracking impact and collating constructive feedback, please complete [this short survey](#) if you plan to use the Framework, and to let me know what you think. Many thanks!

¹ The Framework was devised following a three-stage research project carried out by the author between 2017 and 2019 and presented via Advance HE conferences including [Surveys & Insights 2018](#), [Surveys & Insights 2019](#), [Surveys & Insights 2020](#), [Teaching & Learning 2020](#). The Framework approach, and the documents in it, were piloted, and evaluated, with students in the Law School at the University of Chester during 2017-18 and 2018-19 and led to a dramatic and sustained increase in the department’s NSS scores for Student Voice.

² The Framework documents were peer reviewed during summer 2023 by 17 members of the Staff and Educational Development Association (SEDA). I am very grateful for their comments, which have been incorporated into this version of the Framework and accompanying document pack.